

SKILL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMMES IN INDIA: A CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING

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ABSTRACT

India is one of the youngest countries in the world, our biggest demographic dividend is social and economic asset, with more than 54 per cent of our population youngest than 25 years in age, to entirely comprehend the potential of our youth is vital to furnish them with skills by providing good quality of education, affordable, flexible, and appropriate to the desires of the Indian and worldwide job market. The second largest workforce of the country occupied in the world after China. While China's demographic dividend is expected to start narrowing off by 2015, but India will continue to enjoy it till 2040. The economic survey 2014-15, reveals that India's formally skilled workforce is only 2 per cent which is very low as compared to other countries like China 47 per cent, Japan 80 per cent and South Korea 96 per cent. To strengthen our demographic dividend more substantially and meaningfully, the Government launched the "Skill India" campaign along with "Make in India," Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana, Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gramin Kaushal Yojana, for the skill development of growing youth population of the country

Keywords: India, Skill development, Revolution, Skill India, Employment, skill development programs, , Training, Initiatives.

Methodology The secondary data collected from the Reports of the skill India ministry. Reports of Government of India. Skill India website and books, journal, various websites.

INTRODUCTION

Skill development brought a huge revolution in India. With the introduction of the concept of skill India, the opportunity to develop skills in an individual is at boom. The concept of Skill India and transform India focuses to acquire new age skills that are best suited to meet market demand. There is growth in employment with the implementation of skills in an individual.

Skills may change people's lives and increase the economic productivity of both individuals and society as a whole. People with lower skill levels are more likely to struggle because they are more likely to be unemployed or to be locked in low skill, low income positions. Since they give people the ability to do acceptable employment and enhance their wellbeing, skills can have a profound impact on social behavior. Skills and knowledge are the driving forces of economic growth and social development for any country. In fact, investment made in skills can make countries to invest in social welfare programmes. Lack of the appropriate skills in the workforce can have serious negative impacts on people, societies, and countries. The key that unlocks equitable opportunity for the disadvantaged and underprivileged segments of society can be skilled. The neglected and underprivileged segments of society can move up to the social ladder with equal access to education, training, and work. As India moves progressively towards becoming a 'knowledge economy' it becomes increasingly important that the country should focus on advancement of skills and these skills have to be relevant to the emerging economic environment. In today's rapidly evolving job market,

employers seek candidates with not only academic knowledge but also practical skills that align with industry requirements.

Conceptual Understanding of Skill Development.

Earlier studies for getting insight of the Topic: Vandana Saini (2015) in her study on Skill Development in India: Need, Challenges and Ways forward traced out that both the Government and its partner agencies have undertaken various measures/initiatives for the effective implementation of the skill development system in the economy, but still faces a number of unresolved issues/challenges that need immediate attention of the policy makers. Some extent she identified Challenges before Skill Development Initiatives in India such are Demand & Supply Mismatch Geographical Problem, Low Educational Attainment, Skill development for women, Private sector participation, Placement-linked Challenge, Informal & Formal Sector Skill-Gap, Infrastructure Challenge.

Krishna K, P and Divya Nambiar(2017) In their study on Skill India: Challenges, Achievements and the way forward found that, skills are a key driver of the modern economy. Vocational education and training is aimed at enhancing the employability of an individual's transition into the labour market.

Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship The "Government of India" announced the creation of the first-ever distinct "Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship" in June 2014. It is intended to bring all other ministries together to work in a united manner, establish common standards, and coordinate and streamline the operations of various skill development organizations. The "**Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship**" is responsible for formulating policies related to skill development and entrepreneurship. It coordinates all aspects of skill development initiatives of other ministries and agencies. The ministry is responsible for fulfilling the industrial demand of the skilled labor force in the country, to raise funds to operate the Skill Development Scheme in 2009. The funds are collected from several government sources and non-government sources with the help of NSDF to realize the objectives of the skill development schemes in India.

Schemes for Skill Development in India:

National Skill Development Mission On "World Youth Skills Day" on July 15, 2015, the Hon'ble Prime Minister inaugurated the "National Skill Development Mission" (NSDM). The "National Skill Development Mission" intends to provide a solid institutional framework for skilling efforts in the country, both at the national and state level. The mission's decision-making system is three-tiered and high-powered. The Governing Council of the Mission, chaired by the Prime Minister, aims to give comprehensive guidance and policy direction. The "Steering Committee," chaired by the "Minister in Charge of Skill Development," intends to review the mission's actions in accordance with the Governing Council's directive. The Mission Directorate, led by the Secretary of State for Skill Development, ensures that skilling programmes are implemented, coordinated, and converged across all Central Ministries/Departments and State Governments. In addition, the mission includes a number of submissions in high priority sectors.

SANKALP

Skills Acquisition and Knowledge Awareness for Livelihood Promotion (SANKALP) project aims to implement the mandate of the **National Skill Development Mission** (NSDM), which was launched on 15th July by Ministry of Skill Development & Entrepreneurship, through its core sub-missions. The project will be implemented in mission mode through World Bank support and is aligned with the overall objectives of the NSDM. The main objectives of the

project include strengthening institutional mechanisms at both national and state levels, building a pool of quality trainers and assessors, creating convergence among all skill training activities at the state level, establishing robust monitoring and evaluation system for skill training programs, providing access to skill training opportunities to the disadvantaged sections and most importantly supplement the Make in India initiative by catering to the skill requirements in relevant manufacturing sectors.

Innovation

The National Skill Development Agency, invites innovative ideas, concepts and practices on skill development. A committee has been set up to review all such innovations and to facilitate their application on a wider scale. All the innovators who wish to bring their ideas and practices may send their proposals and presentation to the National Skill Development Agency via email to innovations@nsda.net.in. Shortlisted proposals will be invited to make presentation before the Committee which will meet every month on the third Wednesday of the month at 11 am in the NSDA office, commencing from 17th Dec 2014. Selected innovative practices will be facilitated and propagated for wider application.

World Skills

World Skills India is an initiative of the National Skill Development Corporation (NSDC) under the Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship. NSDC, through its World Skills India initiative, has been the key objectives of World Skills India are to:

- (i) Promulgate skills in the society and motivate the youth to pursue vocational education.
- (ii) Champion skills and learning for work through local, regional, national and international skills competition and contribute to the societies leading the country's participation at World Skills International competitions since 2011.
- (iii) Invite sponsorships to organize the local, regional, national and international skills competitions and also host international competitions.
- (iv) Establish links and a long-term association with the WSI secretariat along with development of cooperation with the Government of India, state Governments, registered vocational skills training and awarding bodies.

National Skill Development Corporation (NSDC) The "National Skill Development Corporation of India," founded in 2009, is a one-of-a-kind non-profit organization established by the "Ministry of Finance." The NSDC was established as part of a national skill development mission to meet India's growing demand for skilled workers across sectors. The organization helps to reduce the skill gap that exists in the industry. It works as a Public-Private Partnership (PPP) in India. The NSDC plays a pivotal role in financing selected private training initiatives. / Schemes to develop an ecosystem to train the youth of the nation. These schemes include the "Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana" (PMKVY), Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Kendra (PMKK), and the National Apprenticeship Promotion Scheme (NAPS). Further, a skills development institute needs various inputs or support services to function properly. These include curriculum, faculty training, standards, quality assurance procedures, technology platforms, advocacy support, and so on. Therefore, NSDC also supports improving the quality of skill training through establishing standards and accrediting systems in partnership with various industry associations.

Schemes and initiative run by the NSDC

1. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY)
2. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Kendras (PMKK)
3. Rozgar Mela
4. Capacity Building Scheme
5. School Initiatives
6. Higher Education
7. NSDC Collaborations
8. India International Skill Centers (IISCs)
9. Pre-Departure Orientation Training (PDOT)

Sector Skill Councils (SSC) The National Skill Development Corporation establishes Sector Skill Councils (SSCs) as not-for-profit organisations. The expert in that sector individually directs the sector. The responsibilities of the SSC are to develop and implement occupational standards, develop and implement competency frameworks, and train the trainer programmes and certify the trainees on the curriculum that is aligned to the national occupational standards

National Skill Development Fund (NSDF) The Government of India established the National Skill Development Fund in 2009 to raise funds for skill development in the country from both the public and private sectors. Various government agencies and others donate to the fund in order to help Indians improve, stimulate, and develop their skills. The funds meet their objective through the NSDC. Further, this fund is managed by a public trust established by the Indian government. The Board of Trustees oversees and manages the fund.

Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY):

This scheme is a flagship outcome based scheme initiated by the Government of India launched in 15 July 2015 with the target to provide to one crore, with the out lay of Rs.12,000 crore to provides skill training youth population in the country. A financial reward is provided to trainees on evaluation of the documentation. For instructions accountable for execution is given by the steering Committee for PMKVY. It has two components as centrally sponsored Centrally Managed (CSCM) being implemented by National Skill Development Corporation (NSDC) and Centrally Sponsored State Managed (CSCM) being implemented by State Skill Development Missions of the States/UTs popularly known as State Engagement Component. Under CSCM Component, 75 per cent of the total funds are provided to NSDC for imparting Fresh Short Term Training (STT) as well as Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL) with the purpose to get better opportunities in terms of placement and self-employment. Industry relevant courses with high employment potential for prospective candidates are being run under the scheme by the Government. Under the Scheme, more than 32 lakh candidates undergoing training and trained so far.

Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gramin Kaushal Yojana (DDU-GKY):

This scheme mainly focuses on providing high quality skill training opportunities through Project Implementing Agencies (PIAs) to rural poor youth, specially focused on women, administered by this scheme under the Ministry of Rural Development. This scheme provides the skill training and placement programme carried out as part of the National Rural Livelihoods Mission. The program provides funding support for placement linked skilling

projects ranging from INR 25,696 per person to over INR 1 lakh. Under this scheme special emphasis has been given to women by reserving 1/3rd of the seats for women, migration support centers are set up to monitor the needs of the vulnerable population, specially women. Special attention is focused on establishing training centers with focus on women trainers in line with the National Policy of Skill Development.

Support to Training and Employment Programme for Women (STEP):

Support to Training and Employment Programme for Women is another one sorts of Central sponsored Scheme running under Ministry of Women and Child Development under this scheme, training is provided to poor and marginalized women in traditional trades to improve employability. The main intention of this scheme is to benefit the women who are in the age group 16 and above. The grants-in-aid are provided by the central government under this programme to societies, voluntary organizations, and cooperatives providing skills in sectors ranging from agriculture to hospitality.

Pradhan Mantri MUDRA Yojana (PMMY):

The MUDRA loan has the objective of funding the unfunded that twin purposes of seeding new enterprises and expanding existing units, with special focus on providing financial support to women entrepreneurs, for both financial inclusion and empowerment. Out of a total 3.49 crore enterprises supported under PMMY during 2015-16 nearly 36% , i.e., 1.25 crore accounts were for first time borrowers

Stand Up India:

Stand Up India scheme has special provisions for women. In this scheme, each bank branch will provide loans of up to Rs 1 crore to at least two such projects per bank branch on an average, one for each category of entrepreneur (SC/ST and Women), in case of firm 51 per cent of shareholding and controlling stake held either by SC/ST or women entrepreneur to ensure financial availability to set up big industries and turn into big entrepreneur.

UDAAN

Udaan is a Special Industry Initiative for Jammu & Kashmir in the nature of partnership between the corporate of India and Ministry of Home Affairs and implemented by National Skill Development Corporation. The programme aims to provide skills training and enhance the employability of unemployed youth of J&K. The Scheme covers graduates, post graduates and three year engineering diploma holders. It has two objectives:

- To provide an exposure to the unemployed graduates to the best of Corporate India;
- To provide Corporate India, an exposure to the rich talent pool available in the State.

The Scheme aims to cover 40,000 youth of J&K over a period of five years and Rs. 750 crore has been earmarked for implementation of the scheme over a period of five years to cover other incidental expenses such as travel cost, boarding and lodging, stipend and travel and medical insurance cost for the trainees and administration cost. Further corporate are eligible for partial reimbursement of training expense incurred for the candidates who have been offered jobs.

CONCLUSION

Skill India offers courses across 40 sectors in the country. The courses help a person focus on practical delivery of work and help him enhance his technical expertise so that he is ready for day one of his job and companies don't have to invest into training him for his job profile. Skill India is no more just limited to the domestic market but is actively engaging with

countries across the world to promote cross geographical exposure and opportunities in the international market. Skill India harbors responsibility for ensuring implementation of Common norms across all skill development programs in the country so that they are all standardized and aligned to one object. The ITI ecosystem has also been brought under Skill India for garnering better results in vocational education and training. The Ministry has also actively made comprehensive reforms to the Apprentices Act 1961, where maximum control has been given to the private sector so that the industry standards are maintained as per market requirement. More regulatory rights have been given to the industry where they can even set the target for apprentices that they require. This is a big opportunity that industry should leverage and benefit

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